

EFFECTS OF THERMAL CYCLING ON DIMENSION

OF FIBROUS METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Sokichi Umekawa¹⁾, Kenji Wakashima²⁾ and Shinichi Yoda³⁾

1. Professor, 2. Associate, 3. Graduate Student
at Research Laboratory of Precision Machinery
and Electronics, Tokyo Institute of Technology
4259 Nagatsuta, Midori-ku, Yokohama 227, Japan

The changes in dimension and shape of the FRM for the thermal cyclings were exercised on the directionally solidified Al_3Ni-Al eutectic alloys and on the aligned $W-Cu$ composites with special emphasis on the interfacial problems. Verification of the validity of the results with the Al_3Ni-Al eutectic alloys were further demonstrated with the $W-Cu$ composites.

The Al_3Ni-Al specimens were thermally cycled between 0.5 and 0.8 of the matrix homologous temperature up to 1400 times. Within the temperature range, every cycle performed a hysteresis loop. With increasing number of cycles, the dimension in the fiber direction exhibited gradual growth, maintaining the shape of hysteresis loop almost equal. The composite was finally expanded in the fiber direction and the transverse section was severely distorted. The distribution and orientation of the Al_3Ni phase were closely related to the nonuniform deformation in the sections which were initially of a round figure. The effects of thermal cyclings were exaggerated for the $W-Cu$ composites with V_f of 0.1 and 0.52. The final figure of the specimen with $V_f=0.1$ subjected 4600 thermal cycles between 0.35 and 0.8 T_m of Cu (specimen (a)) was compared with that of 4950 cycles between 0.5 and 0.8 T_m (specimen (b)). The effect of the extension of the temperature was so surprising, that the strain of specimen (b) was few percent, whereas that of specimen (a) was a several hundreds percent. The effect of thermal cycling on the longitudinal growth depends on the length, diameter and volume fraction of fiber and the thermal conditions.

The instability of the dimension/shape of the directional FRM is presumably due to the interfacial sliding in addition to the plasto-elastic deformation of the matrix. By assuming a quasiviscous behavior of the interface boundary layers, a simplified theory based on a one-dimensional model for a theoretical consideration of the sliding was proposed.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced metallic composites are usually fabricated at elevated temperature and expected for the high temperature uses. Accordingly, the thermal expansion mismatch between the matrix and the fiber is the most important and serious problem for the FRM[1-3]. On cooling, after completed the fabrication, most matrices are deformed elastically or plasto-elastic-

ly resulting residual stress at ambient temperature. At elevated temperature, the effect of the thermally induced stress would presumably be easier to decrease with the aid of slip and creep of the matrix/interface. The thermal expansion mismatch of the constituents of FRM tends to degrade the composite properties, occasionally accompanies localized deformation and even micro-cracking in matrix [4].

Such a tendency is an intrinsic feature of aligned FRM, especially predominates for the repeated heating and cooling. The composite more or less changes its dimension and shape as well as the mechanical properties for the thermal cyclings [5-12].

The turbine-blade materials, for example, undergo high temperature exposure and a number of thermal cycles. That kind of behaviors, therefore, should be investigated in detail for the wide usage of the FRM.

In this paper, the effects of thermal cycling on the dimension of FRM are principally described. Then, the changes in the size/shape and in the microscopic structure of the composites as the result of the numerous thermal cycles are illustrated for the composite factors such as length, diameter and volume fraction of fibers, under several thermal conditions. Experimental studies have been carried out with unidirectionally solidified Al_3Ni-Al eutectic alloy. Verification of the validity of the results is further experimentally demonstrated with the W-Cu composites and theoretical consideration based on the interfacial sliding is discussed. Although both the Al_3Ni-Al and the W-Cu systems are of little engineering use, such composites would be useful for the study on the thermal behaviors as model materials.

Experimental Procedure

Al_3Ni-Al System

Eutectic master alloy (6.1 Wt % Ni-Al) was prepared from electrolytic 99.97%Ni and 99.999%Al by the use of a high frequency furnace. Directional solidification was accomplished at cooling rate of 3.3×10^{-3} cm/sec in argon atmosphere with temperature gradient at the solid-liquid interface of 85-55 K/cm.

Thermal expansion specimens of 50mm long, 5mm square thus solidified were thermally cycled between 448 and 748K which correspond to 0.5 and 0.8 of the matrix homologous temperature up to 1400 times at a rate of 3 cycles/hr in argon flow by the use of infrared reflection furnace.

The *in situ* measurement of the length was recorded with the differential quartz tube dilatometer and X-Y recorder.

W-Cu Composites

The unidirectional composites with 99.9%FHC Cu matrix and W wires of 0.04mm and 0.1mm diameter were fabricated by means of vacuum infiltration at 1160°C and cooling rate at 0.5cm/min. The specimen sizes are 10, 30 and 60mm long with 5×5 mm cross section and the W wires in the longitudinal direction. The specimens of $V_f=0.1$ and $V_f=0.52$ of W wire with 0.1mm and 0.04mm diameter were individually vacuum-sealed in quartz tubes at the pressure of 0.1 Pa for the thermal cyclings. The thermal cycling was carried out automatically between 1073K and 673K which correspond to 0.8 and 0.5 of the melting point of Cu (T_m) respectively (cycle type A), or 1073K and 473K (0.35 T_m) (cycle type B).

The periods of time in which the specimens being held at the top and the bottom temperatures are controlled for a certain duration (cycle type C, for example). The scheme of the cycle types are shown in Fig. 1. The residual strains were measured by micrometer/electric-micrometer. Microstructures were observed by the scanning electron microscope.

Experimental Results

Al₃Ni-Al System

The diameter and the spacing of the fibrous Al₃Ni in the unidirectionally solidified composite were 1.0 μm and 3 μm, respectively. Uniform distribution of the aligned Al₃Ni phase in the material was obtained in the middle portion of the ingots. Differently oriented groups of layered colonies in the transverse section, however, were observed at the end of middle to very end region in the longitudinal direction.

The typical example of the thermal cyclings vs. strains, is shown in Fig. 2. As a matter of fact each cycle performs a hysteresis loop. The formation of the hysteresis loop is an essential characteristic of aligned fibrous composite [13-15]. For the advance of cycles the loops being upward, keeping their shapes equal. That is, a continuing elongation in the solidification direction took place by the thermal cycling between 448 and 748K. The rate of the directional growth was 7.5 microstrain/cycle up to 700 cycles and subsequently increased to 17.0 microstrain/cycle. The final figure of the composite specimen undergone for 1400 thermal cycles was prolonged and severely distorted with contrast to Al specimen as shown in Fig. 3. Optical micrograph of the transverse section in the vicinity of the bottom end of the specimen at the right of Fig. 3 is shown in Fig. 4. The figure, of course, was initially a right circle has been distorted.

Fig.1 Schematic representation of the thermal cycle.

Fig.2 Dimensional changes vs. thermal cycles in a directionally solidified Al₃Ni-Al alloy.

Fig.3 Final figure of the directionally solidified $\text{Al}_3\text{Ni-Al}$ composite (the right), and that of Al (the left), subjected to 1400 thermal cycles between 448 and 748°K.

Fig.4 Optical micrograph of the transverse section of the specimen shown at the right of Fig. 3.

10 μm

100 μm

Fig.5 Scanning electron microscopy of the end surface of $\text{Al}_3\text{Ni-Al}$ specimen after thermal cycling. (low at right and high at left magnification)

The distribution and orientation of Al_3Ni phase in the transverse section were closely related to a nonuniform deformation of thermal cycled alloy. Observation of the optical microscopy of the transverse section shows that the deformation was related with the microstructure which was characterized by the differently oriented groups of layered colonies. At the end of the specimen, displacement between Al_3Ni phase and the matrix was observed. As the result of the relative intrusion of the fibers, the initially polished flat surface is crumpled up. The SEM picture of the end surface of the specimen after thermal cycling test as shown in Fig. 5, illustrates deep holes at the fiber sites.

W-Cu Composite

There appeared an offset at the fiber-matrix interface indicating the sliding as well as the matrix deformation in the thermal cycled composite. The offset continuously grew up with increasing the number of cycles. The final figure of the specimen subjected 4600 thermal cycles between 473 and 1073K (cycle type B) was compared with that of 4950 cycles between 673 and 1073°K (cycle type A) as shown in Fig. 6.

The specimens contain 0.1 V_f of W wire and initial length was 30mm. The effect of the extension of temperature range (200K to the lower side in cycle type B) on the deformation was quite surprising, the specimen progressively grown in longitudinal direction to several hundreds percent had finally been buckled by the capsule. The fibers remained in the original length with any breakdown. Figure 7 shows the longitudinal section at the end of the specimen subjected cycle type A as shown at the left of Fig. 6. Preferential growth of the matrix

Fig.6 Final figures of W-Cu composites of $V_f=0.1$
 (1) 4600 cycles 473-1073°K (specimen (a) at the right)
 (2) 4950 cycles 673-1073°K (specimen (b) at the left)

Fig.7 Scanning microscopy of the longitudinal section of specimen (b) in Fig. 6.

along the fiber is observed.

The effect of the holding at the upper temperature of cycling was examined with 0.1 V_f of 0.1mm diameter W wire and 30mm long specimen for cycle type B (without holding) and C (with holding for 600 sec every cycle). The longitudinal growth per unit length depends on holding time at the upper temperature and is small within the initial stage as shown in Fig. 8. The growth per unit length then increases to 1.5×10^{-4} cm/cm per cycle independent of the holding time. For prolonged holding, 10^5 sec for example, at the upper temperature without cycling, any detectable change in dimension was observed.

The growth per unit length is also dependent on such fiber geometries as length l_f , diameter d_f and volume fraction V_f . The effects are illustrated in Fig. 9(a-c) for the specimens with cycle type B. The amount of growth per unit length after a certain number of cycles is greater with shorter length, larger diameter and lower volume fraction of fibers.

Discussion

The effects of thermal cycling on the dimension can be considered with the same principle based on the residual stress caused by the thermal expansion mismatch and the interfacial sliding, for aligned Al_3Ni-Al system and W-Cu composites. Comparison of the Fig. 5 with Fig. 7, and the other experimental result would satisfy the correspondence of the directionally solidified alloy to the W-Cu composite, especially for the interface phenomena.

For the interpretation of such significant dimensional change as in the W-Cu composite after a number of thermal cycles, a mechanism with interfacial sliding may be introduced other than the elasto-plastic behavior of matrix. Although a definite explanation of the evidence is not made yet, it would be reasonable to consider that some factors affecting the sliding, such activation energy, as the equivalent viscosity of the interface and the thickness of the interface which may vary with advanced thermal cycles [4].

Fig.8 Axial growth vs. number of thermal cycles for W-Cu composite with W wire of l_f 30mm, d_f 100 μ m and V_f 0.1.

A misfit strain $\Delta\alpha\Delta T$ would arise between the phases due to the difference $\Delta\alpha$ in their thermal expansion coefficients and the temperature change ΔT . The strain is all cancelled by mechanical strains introduced into the phases, as far as the interphase bond is strong and no sliding takes place at the interface. For an interface which is capable of sliding in a viscous fashion, however, a part of the strain $\Delta\alpha\Delta T$ is cancelled by the mechanical strains. Since one of the phases (the matrix "m") is much weaker than the other (the fibrous reinforcement "f"), the mechanical strain in "m" may be divided into elastic and plastic parts, whereas

that in "f" is purely elastic, as can be justified from the present observations. On the assumption that a simple one-dimensional stress/strain analysis is nearly valid for axial deformation of the specimen, total strains in "m" and "f", ϵ_m^t and ϵ_f^t , can now be written as

$$\epsilon_m^t = \alpha_m(T - T_0) + \epsilon_m^e + \epsilon_m^p, \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_f^t = \alpha_f(T - T_0) + \epsilon_f^e. \quad (2)$$

Fig.9 Axial growth of W-Cu composite with various l_f , d_f and V_f of W wires vs. number of thermal cycles for type B cycling

Here, T_0 is a reference temperature[†] at which the specimen is free from both stress and strain; ϵ^e and ϵ^p are the elastic and the plastic strain, respectively; α is the coefficient of linear thermal expansion; and the subscripts m and f designate the respective phases. Because of phase-boundary sliding, ϵ_m^t is not equated to ϵ_f^t but a strain difference ϵ^s appears between fiber and matrix:

$$\epsilon_m^t - \epsilon_f^t = \epsilon^s . \quad (3)$$

Note that ϵ^s is that part of $\Delta\alpha\Delta T$ which is not cancelled by the mechanical (elastic and/or plastic) strains. Using Hooke's law and static equilibrium condition under no externally applied stress, one easily finds the internal stresses to be expressed in the form:

$$\sigma_m = -(k/V_m)[(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)(T - T_0) + \epsilon_m^p - \epsilon^s] , \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_f = (k/V_f)[(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)(T - T_0) + \epsilon_m^p - \epsilon^s] , \quad (5)$$

where

$$k = V_m V_f E_m E_f / (V_m E_m + V_f E_f) , \quad (6)$$

E is Young's modulus, and V is the fractional phase volume ($V_m + V_f = 1$). It becomes evident from Eqs. (4) and (5) that the internal stresses at a given temperature T are dependent on a difference $\epsilon_m^p - \epsilon^s$ whose amount is unknown up to this point. Considering that phase-boundary sliding as well as plastic deformation of the matrix is an energy-dissipation process, we may employ the principle of virtual work for the determination of $\epsilon_m^p - \epsilon^s$:

$$\delta W^e + \delta W^p + \delta W^s = 0 . \quad (7)$$

Here, W^e is the work stored in the specimen (per unit volume) in the form of elastic strain energy; W^p and W^s are the work lost during plastic deformation of the matrix and during phase-boundary sliding, respectively; and δ indicates the variation of each quantity. The expressions for the first two terms in Eq. (7) are easily obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta W^e &= \delta \left[\frac{1}{2} V_m \sigma_m \epsilon_m^e + \frac{1}{2} V_f \sigma_f \epsilon_f^e \right] \\ &= k [(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)(T - T_0) + \epsilon_m^p - \epsilon^s] (\delta \epsilon_m^p - \delta \epsilon^s) , \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\delta W^p = V_m \sigma_0 |\delta \epsilon_m^p| , \quad (9)$$

where σ_0 is the yield stress of the matrix. On the other hand, the last term in Eq. (7) depends on various sliding models. However, the following expression appears general whatever models are assumed:

$$\delta W^s = \tau^* S \bar{v} \delta t , \quad (10)$$

where τ^* is the effective frictional stress of sliding, S is the total interfacial area per unit volume of the specimen, \bar{v} is the average velocity of sliding, and δt is the infinitesimal time interval. From simple geometric considerations, it follows that $S = 4V_f/d_f$, and $\bar{v} = (\ell_f/4) |\dot{\epsilon}^s|$, where $\dot{\epsilon}^s = d\epsilon^s/dt$, ℓ_f is the fiber length, and d_f is the fiber diameter. Hence:

[†] For the case W-Cu system, T_0 may be taken equal to the melting temperature of copper.

$$\delta W^S = V_f(\lambda_f/d_f)\tau^*|\delta\epsilon^S| . \quad (11)$$

Substituting Eqs. (8), (9) and (11) into Eq. (7), we therefore obtain the following results: During plastic deformation of the matrix, ϵ_m^P varies such that

$$\epsilon_m^P - \epsilon^S = -(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)(T - T_0) \pm (V_m/k)\sigma_0 , \quad (12)$$

whereas during phase-boundary sliding, ϵ^S varies such that

$$\epsilon_m^P - \epsilon^S = -(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)(T - T_0) \pm (V_f/k)(\lambda_f/d_f)\tau^* . \quad (13)$$

For the sign \pm in Eqs. (12) and (13), take plus upon heating and minus upon cooling provided $\alpha_m > \alpha_f$.

Now, for further development of the present analysis, we have to make the assumptions (i) that interfacial sliding is caused by Newtonian flow within a thin phase-boundary layer, and (ii) that temperature is changed stepwise during thermal cycling, as shown in Fig. 10. From assumption (i), it follows that the effective frictional stress τ^* of sliding is expressed in the form:

$$\tau^* = (1/3)\lambda_f(\mu_0/h)|\dot{\epsilon}^S|\exp(Q/RT) , \quad (14)$$

where h is the thickness of phase-boundary layer, μ_0 is a viscosity constant independent of temperature, Q is the activation energy, and R is the gas constant. Substitution of Eq. (14) into Eq. (13) yields a differential equation whose solution is the main concern in the present analysis:

$$\beta\dot{\epsilon}^S + \epsilon^S + \gamma = 0 , \quad (15)$$

where

$$\beta = (1/3)(V_f/k)(\lambda_f^2/d_f)(\mu_0/h)\exp(Q/RT) , \quad (16)^+$$

$$\gamma = -(\alpha_m - \alpha_f)(T - T_0) - \epsilon_m^P . \quad (17)$$

On the basis of assumption (ii), we now analyze deformation behavior of the specimen in the following stages of each temperature cycle: (I) heating from $T_{(-)}$ to $T_{(+)}$, (II) isothermal holding at $T_{(+)}$ for $t_{(+)}$, (III) cooling from $T_{(+)}$ to $T_{(-)}$, and (IV) isothermal holding at $T_{(-)}$ for $t_{(-)}$ (Fig. 10). In state I, interfacial sliding can never occur since the infinite rate of heating causes τ^* to become infinite; but the matrix can plastically deform if $T_{(+)} - T_{(-)}$ is sufficiently large. Then, it follows from Eqs. (4), (5) and (12) that

Fig.10 Thermal cycling pattern adopted present analysis

+ As will be seen later, β corresponds to the so-called relaxation or adjustment time for a viscoelastic substance. [16]

$$\sigma_m = -\sigma_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_f = (V_m/V_f)\sigma_0. \quad (18)^+$$

In stage II, on the other hand, deformation proceeds due entirely to interfacial sliding. Setting $T = T_{(+)}$ and solving Eq. (15) with the initial condition: $\epsilon^S = \epsilon_0^S$ at $t = t_{(+)} = 0$, we have

$$\epsilon^S + \gamma_{(+)} = (\epsilon_0^S + \gamma_{(+)})\exp(-t_{(+)}/\beta_{(+)}) , \quad (19)$$

where $\beta_{(+)}$ and $\gamma_{(+)}$ are the values of β and γ at $T = T_{(+)}$, respectively. It follows from Eqs. (4) and (17) that $\epsilon^S + \gamma_{(+)} = (V_m/k)\sigma_m$; and from Eqs. (12) and (17) that $\epsilon_0^S + \gamma_{(+)} = -(V_m/k)\sigma_0$. Therefore, the compressive stress built up in the matrix upon heating is relaxed such that

$$\sigma_m = -\sigma_0\exp(-t_{(+)}/\beta_{(+)}) , \quad (20)$$

and then ϵ^S increases by the amount of

$$\Delta\epsilon_{(+)}^S = (V_m/k)\sigma_0[1 - \exp(-t_{(+)}/\beta_{(+)})] \quad (21)$$

As is obvious from the above analysis, deformation in the subsequent two stages occurs quite similarly in the reverse direction. Thus, in stage III, the matrix begins to plastically extend after some drop in temperature; then,

$$\sigma_m = \sigma_0 . \quad (22)$$

This tensile stress of the matrix is relaxed in stage IV due to interfacial sliding:

$$\sigma_m = \sigma_0\exp(-t_{(-)}/\beta_{(-)}) , \quad (23)$$

and then ϵ^S decreases by the amount of

$$\Delta\epsilon_{(-)}^S = -(V_m/k)\sigma_0[1 - \exp(-t_{(-)}/\beta_{(-)})] , \quad (24)$$

where $\beta_{(-)}$ is the value of β at $T = T_{(-)}$. Now, it is important to notice that $\Delta\epsilon_{(+)}^S$ increases monotonically with increasing $t_{(+)}/\beta_{(+)}$ until it reaches $(V_m/k)\sigma_0$ asymptotically; and that $\Delta\epsilon_{(-)}^S$ decreases — its negative amount increases — in a similar way. Consequently, the net change in ϵ^S per cycle:

$$\Delta\epsilon^S = \Delta\epsilon_{(+)}^S + \Delta\epsilon_{(-)}^S , \quad (25)$$

does not vanish but takes a positive value provided $t_{(+)}/\beta_{(+)} > t_{(-)}/\beta_{(-)}$.⁺⁺

As shown above, the simplified form of temperature cycles as depicted in Fig. 10 causes the axial dimension of the matrix to progressively increase. The amount of growth per cycle, $\Delta\epsilon^S$, is dependent on cycling variables such as the upper and lower cycling temperatures $T_{(+)}$ and $T_{(-)}$ and the holding times $t_{(+)}$ and $t_{(-)}$ at these temperatures. The higher the upper cycling temperature and/or the lower the lower cycling temperature, the greater the amount of growth per cycle becomes. In other words, when one of the limiting temperatures, either $T_{(+)}$ or $T_{(-)}$, is fixed, a greater amount of $\Delta\epsilon^S$ results from extending the temperature

+ Hereafter the description for σ_f will be omitted, for the relation: $\sigma_f = -(V_m/V_f)\sigma_m$, is always valid.

++ This condition reduces to $\ln(t_{(+)}/t_{(-)}) > (Q/R)(1/T_{(+)} - 1/T_{(-)})$, which is always satisfied unless $t_{(+)} \ll t_{(-)}$.

range of cycling. This qualitatively explains the difference between the experimental results in Figs. 1 and 7. It should be noted, however, that for the continuing growth of the matrix to occur the temperature range of cycling must be large enough to induce plastic deformation of the matrix. Increasing the holding time at $T_{(+)}$ and decreasing that at $T_{(-)}$ also cause the amount of growth per cycle to increase; the former is much more effective than the latter because the relaxation (adjustment) time at $T_{(+)}$, $\beta_{(-)}$, is much smaller than that at $T_{(-)}$, $\beta_{(-)}$. Thus, in most cases of practical interest, where $T_{(-)}$ is sufficiently low and $t_{(-)}$ is not very large, the contribution of $\Delta\epsilon^S_{(-)}$ to $\Delta\epsilon^S$ may be ignored so that

$$\Delta\epsilon^S \approx \Delta\epsilon^S_{(+)} = (V_m/k)\sigma_0[1 - \exp(-t_{(+)}\beta_{(+)})] \quad (26)$$

Obviously, the upper cycling temperature and the holding time there are then the dominant cycling variables. This is in accordance with the general conclusion drawn from previous experiments on thermal cycling damage of metal-matrix composites.

The above expression, Eq. (26), is helpful to the understanding of our experimental observations. The result in Fig. 8 shows that for a given specimen cycled in a given cycling condition the amount of growth (per unit length) per cycle does not always remain constant but rapidly increases to a definite value once the cumulative strain exceeds a certain level. The initial amount tends to increase with increasing the holding time at the upper cycling temperature. However, the final amount does not have such a tendency; It is independent of the holding time at that temperature. This change may probably be attributed to such a decrease in μ_0/h as to reduce the relaxation time $\beta_{(+)}$ to a considerable extent and therefore to make the exponential term of Eq. (26) ineffective. It should be noted that the decrease in μ_0/h results in lowering the effective frictional stress τ^* of interfacial sliding (see Eq. (14)). Eq. (26) then becomes

$$\Delta\epsilon^S \approx (V_m/k)\sigma_0 \quad (27)$$

Using the following values: $E_m = 1.3 \times 10^5$ MPa (assumed), $E_f = 3.8 \times 10^5$ MPa (assumed), $\Delta\epsilon^S = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ cm/cm (observed), and $V_f = 0.1$ ($V_m = 0.9$), we obtain $\sigma_0 \approx 4.8$ MPa. This value is not unreasonable for the yield stress at 1073 K of the matrix material used. Needless to say, Eq. (27) gives the maximum amount of $\Delta\epsilon^S$. Thus, the upper bound for the amount of growth per unit length after N cycles is given by $N(V_m/k)\sigma_0$. It is evident that the broken line in Fig. 8 represents this upper bound for $V_f = 0.1$.

Summary

Two kinds of FRM, Al_3Ni-Al and $W-Cu$ were studied for the effects of thermal cycling on the dimensional change. The responses to the thermal effects were more significant for $W-Cu$ composite than for Al_3Ni-Al system, although both system can be considered on the same mechanism. For the thermal cycling, the dimensional change was characterized by the growth of matrix in fiber axis. The amount of the axial growth increased with the number of thermal cycles. The progressive growth observed was theoretically explained in account for the relaxation of the internal stress generated in the composite due to difference of the thermal expansion of the constituents. The assumption employed in the analysis, especially for the characteristic of boundary layer, was presumably too simplified for the actual case. However, the interface sliding may be an essential feature of composites for thermal cycling at elevated temperature.

References

1. D.A. Koss and S.M. Copley: Met. Trans., 2 (1971), 1557.
2. K. Wakashima, T. Kawakubo and S. Umekawa: Met. Trans. A, 6A (1975), 1755.
3. K. Wakashima and S. Umekawa: Met. Trans. A, 7A (1976), 1952.
4. S. Yoda, N. Kurihara, K. Wakashima and S. Umekawa: Manuscript were submitted to Met. Trans.
5. H. Bibring: Proc. Conf. on in-situ Composites, Vol.2 (1973), 1. Washington.
6. E.M. Breinan, E.R. Thompson and F.D. Lemkey: *ibid*, Vol.2, 201.
7. G. Garmong and C.G. Rhodes: *ibid*, Vol.1, 251.
8. G. Garmong: Met. Trans., 5 (1974), 2199.
9. F.M. Dunlevey and J.F. Wallace: *ibid*, 1351.
10. M.A. Wright: *ibid*, 6A (1975), 129.
11. K.K. Chawla: J. Mater. Sci., 11 (1976), 1567.
12. N.A. Flanders, D.M.R. Taplin and H.W. Kerr: *ibid*, 2051.
13. A.R.T. de Silva and G.A. Chadwick: J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 17 (1969), 387.
14. G. Garmong: Met. Trans., 5 (1974), 2183.
15. K. Wakashima, M. Otsuka and S. Umekawa: J. Comp. Mater., 8 (1974), 391.
16. A. Nadai, Theory of Flow and Fracture of Solids, Vol.2, 157, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1963.